

Optimal Hiding of Quantum Information

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Abstract. Decoupling is the task of erasing the correlations that an object system, accessible to us, has established with a remote reference system. This task has fundamental applications in a wide number of fields, such as quantum secure communication, thermodynamics, and black-hole radiation. When faced with the problem of erasing correlations, the direct approach is “to dump” them in the environment, that is, to hand them over to an eavesdropper. A variant of decoupling is *quantum hiding*, where the goal is again to decouple the system from the reference, but this time maintaining *also* its local environment decoupled from the reference [Braunstein, Pati; PRL 2007].

Here, by building upon the paradigm of *private quantum decoupling* [Buscemi; NJP 2009], I formalize the information-theoretic task of *optimal quantum hiding* and provide a single-letter formula for its optimal rate in the asymptotic i.i.d. setting. It turns out that the total amount of correlations present in the initial state is divided into “extrinsic” (hidable) and “intrinsic” (non hidable) ones, the latter being equal to the coherent information (which is thus equipped with a new operational interpretation). Connections with entanglement theory are finally discussed.

Keywords: optimal quantum hiding, private quantum decoupling, coherent information

Let us suppose we are given a medium containing sensitive information which, for some reason, we want to dispose of in a secure way, i.e., in such a way that neither we nor anyone else can have access to—or be deemed to possess—that information anymore. When dealing with macroscopic objects, the irreversibility of dissipative processes (like, e.g., destroying the media itself) is generally enough to provide a *practically secure* erasure of data. In principle, however, one could argue that, microscopic evolutions being fundamentally reversible, information ought to be globally preserved, thus effectively forbidding any sort of *true* information erasure [13, 9, 12]. Even so, however, information could be, if not erased, at least “hidden,” or encoded in such a way to achieve what a secure disposal of information is meant to achieve [1, 8, 3].

In what follows, I start from the task of quantum hiding, introduced in Ref. [1] for pure states, and generalize it to the information-theoretic task of *optimal quantum hiding*. The latter constitutes a novel instance of the general task of *decoupling*, that is, producing—under various constraints—an uncorrelated (i.e., factorized) state out of a correlated one. The importance of studying decoupling protocols lies in the fact that, with appropriate constraints, it is possible to quantitatively characterize diverse properties of quantum correlations with respect to their robustness *against* decoupling. Such an approach has been introduced independently in Refs. [5] and [10], and contributed in recognizing the central role that decoupling plays in quantum information processing: for example, both primitives of state merging [11] and state redistribution [4] are based on decoupling arguments, and decoupling procedures form the building blocks of many coding theorems achieving quantum capacity (see, e.g., Ref. [14, 6, 15]).

Hence, optimal quantum hiding offers a new point of view on the study of quantum decoupling and quantum correlations, with possible implications in various areas

of quantum information sciences, ranging from quantum cryptography to quantum thermodynamics, and possibly including even more exotic problems like black holes evaporation and its relations with the foundations of quantum theory [2].

1 Formalization

Let ϱ_{RA} be the density operator representing the initial bipartite state shared between two parties—an accessible system A (with Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_A) and an inaccessible reference R (with Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_R). Paraphrasing Ref. [1], *perfect hiding* is achieved if there exists a bipartite isometric splitting $V : \mathcal{H}_A \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_B \otimes \mathcal{H}_E$, with $V^\dagger V = \mathbb{1}_A$, such that the following two conditions are simultaneously satisfied:

1. **Decoupling:** the output system B is decoupled from the reference R ; in formula: $\text{Tr}_E[(\mathbb{1}_R \otimes V_A)\varrho_{RA}(\mathbb{1}_R \otimes V_A)^\dagger] = \varrho_R \otimes \sigma_B$, for some σ_B .
2. **Privacy:** the environment E is decoupled from the reference R ; in formula: $\text{Tr}_B[(\mathbb{1}_R \otimes V_A)\varrho_{RA}(\mathbb{1}_R \otimes V_A)^\dagger] = \varrho_R \otimes \sigma_E$, for some σ_E .

Leveraging on the well known relation between quantum mutual information and trace distance, that is [15]

$$I(X; Y) \geq \frac{1}{2 \ln 2} \|\tau_{XY} - \tau_X \otimes \tau_Y\|_1^2, \quad (1)$$

we define perfect hiding in an information-theoretic language as follows:

Definition 1 (Perfect Hiding) *We say that the correlations present in a state ϱ_{RA} can be perfectly hidden, whenever there exists an isometric splitting of A , $V : A \rightarrow BE$, such that $I(R; B) = I(R; E) = 0$, where the two quantum mutual informations are computed with respect to the final tripartite state $\sigma_{RBE} := (\mathbb{1}_R \otimes V_A)\varrho_{RA}(\mathbb{1}_R \otimes V_A)^\dagger$.*

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Generally speaking, perfect hiding is not possible. As an example, let us consider an initial pure bipartite state $|\Psi_{RA}\rangle$. Any isometric splitting produces a tripartite pure state $|\Psi'_{RBE}\rangle := (\mathbb{1}_R \otimes V_A)|\Psi_{RA}\rangle$. Then, a trivial calculation tells us that

$$\underbrace{I(R; B)}_{\text{decoupling}} + \underbrace{I(R; E)}_{\text{privacy}} = 2H(R) = I(R; A), \quad (2)$$

that is, the two notions of privacy and decoupling obey a tradeoff relation, making them *incompatible*—using the language of entropic uncertainty relations. It is then meaningful to introduce the idea of *optimal tradeoff*:

Definition 2 (Intrinsic Correlations) *Given a bipartite state ϱ_{RA} , we introduce the following quantity:*

$$\xi(\varrho_{RA}) := \inf_{V:A \rightarrow BE} \left\{ I(R; B) + I(R; E) \right\}, \quad (3)$$

where the infimum is taken over all possible isometric splitting $V : A \rightarrow BE$. We say that the quantity $\xi(\varrho_{RA})$ measures the amount of intrinsic correlations contained in ϱ_{RA} . Its regularization is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \xi^\infty(\varrho_{RA}) &:= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \xi(\varrho_{RA}^{\otimes n}) \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \inf_{V:A^n \rightarrow B^n E^n} \left\{ I(R^n; B^n) + I(R^n; E^n) \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where the mutual informations are computed with respect to the multipartite output state

$$\sigma_{R^n B^n E^n} := (\mathbb{1}_{R^n} \otimes V_{A^n})(\varrho_{RA}^{\otimes n})(\mathbb{1}_{R^n} \otimes V_{A^n})^\dagger,$$

and the infimum is taken over all bipartite splitting $V : A^n \rightarrow B^n E^n$, which are free to act globally on the whole input Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_A^{\otimes n}$.

Notice that, in the above definition, the output state $\sigma_{R^n B^n E^n}$ may well be entangled across the many-copy systems $B^n E^n$.

It should be clear that the intrinsic correlations $\xi(\varrho_{RA})$ are crucial to the problem of quantum hiding: they are zero if and only if the correlations in ϱ_{RA} are perfectly hidable, and they characterize the tradeoff between privacy and decoupling in state ϱ_{RA} .

2 The Results

Proposition 3 (Converse Bounds) *For any bipartite state ϱ_{RA} and any isometric splitting $V : A \rightarrow BE$, the following bounds hold:*

$$I(R; B) \geq I_c(A)R + H(B) - H(E), \quad (5)$$

$$I(R; E) \geq I_c(A)R + H(E) - H(B), \quad (6)$$

where $I_c(A)R := -H(A|R)$ is the $A \rightarrow R$ coherent information of state ϱ_{RA} .

The above bounds imply, in particular, that

$$\xi(\varrho_{RA}) \geq 2I_c(A)R. \quad (7)$$

Moreover, since the coherent information is additive on tensor-product states, we have that the same bound also holds for the regularized version:

$$\xi^\infty(\varrho_{RA}) \geq 2I_c(A)R. \quad (8)$$

Proposition 4 (Achievability Bounds) *For any bipartite state ϱ_{RA} , there exists a bipartite splitting $V : A \rightarrow BE$ such that, simultaneously,*

$$I(R; B) \leq \frac{1}{2}I(R; A), \quad (9)$$

$$I(R; E) \leq \frac{1}{2}I(R; A). \quad (10)$$

In the asymptotic i.i.d. setting, it is possible to tighten the above bounds and obtain the optimal rate as

$$\xi^\infty(\varrho_{RA}) = \max\{2I_c(A)R, 0\}. \quad (11)$$

We thus have that the regularized intrinsic correlations are completely characterized in terms of a single-letter formula, which also provides the coherent information with a new operational interpretation.

Remark 1 (About the gap) *Asymptotically one can do better than one-shot: this fact is a consequence of the inequality $2I_c(A)R \leq I(R; A)$. Indeed, for large dimensions, the gap may become generically large, i.e., $2I_c(A)R \ll I(R; A)$, see Ref. [7].*

Remark 2 (When are correlations all intrinsic?)

Eq. (11) above informs us also about the cases in which correlations cannot be hidden, but only transferred to the environment. This happens whenever $2I_c(A)R = I(R; A)$, namely, when $H(RA) = H(R) - H(A)$. This condition can be easily understood by introducing an ancilla Z purifying the initial state ϱ_{RA} ; then, $H(RA) = H(R) - H(A)$ is equivalent to $I(Z; A) = 0$, that is, $\varrho_{ZA} = \varrho_Z \otimes \varrho_A$. That is, all correlations are intrinsic if and only if the accessible system A is purified by a subsystem of the reference R .

3 Discussion

We saw that regularized intrinsic correlations can be characterized in terms of a single-letter formula and that this equals the coherent information, which is known to appear also in many other quantum information-theoretic protocols. As a consequence, since all separable states have zero coherent information, we see that separable correlations are always perfectly hidable. However, not only separable correlations are perfectly hidable, but also bound entangled ones (that is, entangled states from which no entanglement can be distilled). Correspondingly, the presence of non-zero intrinsic correlations implied, via the hashing bound $E_D \geq I_c$, that entanglement can be distilled from ϱ_{RA} at non-zero rate. In this sense, intrinsic correlations are *genuinely quantum correlations* and constitute an entanglement parameter (in the precise sense that, the larger they are, the more entangled is a state).

An open problem is to find one-shot bounds which are tighter than those provided in Eq. (9).

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